

Abstract/Title: (pazopanib OR Votrient) AND (therapeutic drug monitoring OR TDM OR plasma levels OR concentration OR exposure OR precision medicine OR individualized therapy OR personalized dosing OR drug monitoring)

Identification
*Performed by 30th
June 2023*

Screening

In-depth review

**Data analysis, extraction,
description, tabulation**

*J.J. and M.T.; accordingly with pre-defined inclusion and exclusion criteria indicated in the „Methods“ section